

The logo features a large, light blue, rounded shape resembling a drop or a wave. Below it, there is a smaller, darker blue wave-like shape with a trail of seven dark blue circles of varying sizes, suggesting movement or a path.

EVOLVE2CARE

KPI framework

(Living Labs, End-Users, Impact Assessment)

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Executive Summary

The **EVOLVE2CARE Key Performance Indicator (KPI) Framework** has been developed to support the effective monitoring and evaluation of health technology innovations co-created and tested within Living Labs. Developed after a comprehensive analysis of stakeholder needs and systemic barriers, the framework aims to assess the value, usability, and impact of collaborative innovation in transitional healthcare settings.

The framework is structured around **three distinct repositories**:

1) Use Case Evaluation KPI Repository

Focused on the collaboration between Living Labs and innovators, this repository includes KPIs that measure the effectiveness of user involvement, real-life testing, legal and ethical compliance, access to data, and scale-up support. It reflects the multidimensional value Living Labs bring to innovation ecosystems, emphasizing their role in providing infrastructure, expertise, and real-world validation environments.

2) End-User KPI Repository

This section identifies KPIs specific to the needs of patients, caregivers, healthcare professionals, and healthcare organizations. It evaluates whether innovations truly reduce workload, enhance care continuity, improve decision-making through predictive analytics and remote monitoring, and promote active user engagement and empowerment.

3) Impact Assessment KPI Repository

Going beyond individual cases, this repository examines the broader technical, fiscal, environmental, social, and regulatory impacts of EVOLVE2CARE. It introduces indicators such as usability, integration speed, regulatory readiness, cost-effectiveness, inclusivity, and ecological sustainability to ensure a holistic understanding of innovation outcomes.

The framework is designed to guide continuous improvement, providing a practical foundation for stakeholders to align innovation efforts with real-world challenges, fostering more effective, inclusive, and scalable health solutions.

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1. Structure of the Framework

The barriers and enablers analysis conducted served as the basis for identifying the specific needs of each group. These needs were further analysed to determine which stakeholder group and category they belong to. We then identified the purpose each need serves:

1. The broader scope of technical, economic, environmental, and social impact of collaboration between Living Labs and Tech Innovators.
2. Directly addressing HealthTech solutions in transitional care

This led to the development of **two distinct Key Performance Indicator (KPI) repositories**:

1. **Use Case Evaluation KPI Repository** – Designed to **assess the effectiveness of individual collaborations** between Living Labs (LLs) and innovators, ensuring that innovations are effectively developed and validated.
2. **Impact Assessment KPI Repository** – Focused on **evaluating the overall impact**, considering factors such as technological advancements, financial sustainability, operational efficiency, and regulatory compliance.

The **Use Case Evaluation KPI Repository** was structured based on two key stakeholder groups:

- **Collaboration between Living Labs and innovators:** Living Labs provide critical resources, infrastructure, and expertise to innovators. In return, innovators require targeted support to accelerate the development and adoption of their solutions. The corresponding **KPIs measure how effectively LLs support innovators** and **how well innovators leverage LL resources**.
- **Alignment with broader stakeholder needs:** Innovations must address the needs of healthcare professionals, caregivers, patients, and healthcare institutions. The corresponding **KPIs assess how well innovations align with real-world challenges** in transitional care.

The **Impact Assessment KPI Repository**, evaluates EVOLVE2CARE at a broader level, measuring its contributions to:

- **Technological advancements** – How the program fosters innovation.
- **Financial sustainability** – The viability and scalability of solutions.
- **Operational efficiency** – How efficiently Living Labs and Innovators function.
- **Regulatory compliance** – The alignment of innovations with healthcare policies.

KPI repositories serve as guiding tools rather than rigid benchmarks, allowing innovators to refine their solutions based on structured feedback rather than compliance pressures.

Figure 1 - KPI Framework Visualization

2. KPI Repository Framework

2.1. Living Labs

To understand the value Living Labs bring to innovation ecosystems, the framework analysed expectations and experiences of researchers participating in Living Lab activities. Thematic and content analysis techniques were applied to qualitative data, identifying core themes that guided the development of relevant KPIs.

These KPIs are grouped into the following key areas:

Table 1 - KPIs for Living Labs (LLs)

Categories	KPI
<p>User recruitment & involvement: get feedback from user, involve them in the process, handle the recruitment.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders from the 4-druple helix are actively involved in the feedback process and innovation development. • Measure the level of involvement of stakeholders in Living Lab Activities.

<p>Legal, regulation & safety standard support: related to ethics, legal issues, privacy</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovations meet legal, ethical, privacy, and safety standards throughout their development and deployment.
<p>Real life testing & Experimentation: all the activities that have to do with testing, piloting, experimenting, and experimentation design.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real-life testing or experimentation activities that meet predefined goals or objectives.
<p>Collaboration & Networking possibilities: create new opportunities for collaboration, synergies and networking.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New partnerships or synergies established through networking activities. • Quantify Knowledge exchange in collaboration and networking activities.
<p>Access to existing data and data analysis methods: either get access to existing data or collect a new dataset. It includes also the expertise for data analysis.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovators gain access to relevant existing data or have successfully collected new datasets for analysis • FAIR Data compliance for Living Lab data (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of Digital Assets) • Regulatory and Ethical Compliance for Living Lab data
<p>Knowledge acquired experience & Learning: get the knowledge, learn methodologies and experience the LL way of working, get insights or understanding that comes from active experimentation. Insights are from users and their perspective.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovators gain new insights or methodologies through active experimentation.
<p>Business & Scale-up support: expand or get access to new markets, scale-up an existing solution.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovations successfully expanded into new markets or scaled up for wider adoption. • Validating market readiness using frameworks like the Market readiness level.
<p>Diversity of opinions & New Context: cultural, social context, experience from new countries, language – multistakeholder</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovators gain access and insights into feedback from diverse cultural, social, and geographical contexts.

<p>Expert opinion & Advisory services: learn from experts, get guidance and support and expert opinion including from external stakeholders' network, refers to giving advice and consulting and not direct hands-on experience. Advice is from experts in another sector, different than yours.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advisory sessions or expert consultations received by innovators from external stakeholders or industry professionals.
<p>Physical space, equipment & facilities: providing the technology, infrastructure resources and technical facilities to perform the work.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical space, equipment, and facilities are open, available effectively utilized for innovation development.
<p>Publications</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peer-reviewed publications demonstrating the effects and efficiency of the innovation.

2.2. End-users

This part of the framework focuses on the diverse needs of four end-user groups: patients, caregivers, healthcare professionals, and healthcare organisations. General needs were initially derived from barrier and enabler analysis and then triangulated with influential literature and established frameworks. The KPIs include:

Table 2 - KPIs for End-Users

Stake holder	Need	KPI
Healthcare professionals	Need innovations that reduce, rather than increase, their workload, streamlining processes and improving efficiency to allow for more focus on patient care.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decrease in time spent on administrative or repetitive tasks due to the implementation of innovative solutions, measured through feedback or time tracking. • No significant increase in workload following the introduction of an innovative solution, measured through feedback or time tracking.
Healthcare professionals	Need centralized digital health platforms that integrate various services and data making access to information easy.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New innovations are seamlessly integrated into centralized platforms instead of introducing a new platform every time.
	Need decision support tools that enhance their knowledge by providing access to new, relevant information.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regular use of decision support tools by healthcare professionals • Healthcare professionals reporting improved clinical decisions as a result of using decision support tools.
	Need wearables and assistive technologies that help them track more information, enhance patient monitoring, and support their work in real-time.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Average rating given by healthcare professionals on the usefulness of wearables/assistive technologies in enhancing patient care and supporting their workflow, gathered through surveys or feedback.

Healthcare professionals	<p>Need remote patient monitoring tools that allow them to track patients' health when they do not have direct access.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More timely and continuous interventions for patients as a result of using remote patient monitoring tools, reported by healthcare professionals • Healthcare professionals report being able to respond to critical situations or patient changes that they would not have detected without the use of remote patient monitoring tools.
	<p>Need predictive analytics tools that help anticipate patient outcomes and risks, enabling proactive and data-driven decision-making.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Predictive analytics tools accurately forecast patient outcomes or risks. • Predictions lead to proactive interventions. • Predictive analytics models incorporate data from multiple sources (e.g., patient history, real-time monitoring, lab results) to enhance the accuracy and reliability of predictions. • Re-admission rates and complication rates as indicators of improved outcomes.
Healthcare professionals	<p>Need scientifically validated solutions that are proven to be effective through rigorous research.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peer-reviewed publications demonstrating the scientific validation and effectiveness of the solution in real-world healthcare settings.

	Need training and education on new technologies to enhance their skills and improve the effective use of innovative solutions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved proficiency and confidence of healthcare professionals in using new technologies.
Hospitals / Organisations	Need innovations that streamline processes and enhance overall operational performance.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduction in time spent on administrative or repetitive tasks due to improved workflows.
	Cost-effective innovations that are proven through evidence to improve patient care and outcomes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ratio of cost savings to improvements in patient outcomes achieved by the innovation.
	Innovations should integrate smoothly into current hospital systems and practices, minimizing disruption.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Average time taken to fully integrate an innovation into existing workflows, from introduction to full implementation. Time for personnel to get used to new systems and work efficiently.
	Adoption is based on strategy (top-down vs User Satisfaction).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Comparison of adoption effectiveness based on top-down strategy vs. user satisfaction.
	Need innovations that assist in creating and following discharge planning protocols, ensuring smooth transitions for patients.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Patients reporting better continuity of care and smoother transitions post-discharge, due to the implementation of discharge planning innovations.
Patients	Need innovations that prioritize their needs, involve them in decision-making, and encourage active participation in their care.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrating respect for patients as partners in developing care plans reflective of their goals.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continuously evaluating patients' levels of engagement
	Solutions that directly contribute to improved health outcomes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Health indicators for transitional care Qol Re-hospitalization Length of stay Functional status and independence
	Need training and education on new technologies to enhance their skills and improve the effective use of innovative solutions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved proficiency and confidence of patients in using new technologies
	Need understandable care models and processes, along with effective medication management systems, to ensure they can follow their treatment plans confidently and manage their health effectively.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presenting health information in easily accessible, accurate, and usable formats Monitoring to avoid medication errors Ensuring that medication management plan is based on evidence
Patients	Ensuring that medication management plan is based on evidence (TCC).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensuring that medication management plan is based on evidence
	Personalized care that is tailored to their unique health conditions, preferences, and circumstances, ensuring more effective and individualized treatment.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Patients feel that their personal health needs and preferences are effectively addressed through the personalized care provided, as measured through surveys or direct feedback. Direct measurement of perceived balance between digital solutions and human interaction.
Caregivers	Need support and resources to reduce the physical, emotional, and financial burden associated with caregiving.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Decrease in caregiving burden measured through caregiver satisfaction

		surveys or specific burden assessment tools.
Caregivers	Need to be actively engaged in the caregiving process, with opportunities for involvement in care decisions, training, and support systems.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrating respect for caregivers as partners in developing care plans reflective of their goals. • Continuously evaluating caregivers' levels of engagement.
	Need training and education on new technologies to enhance their skills and improve the effective use of innovative solutions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved proficiency and confidence of caregivers in using new technologies. • Measurable impact of educational tools in reducing caregiver burden.

2.3. Impact Assessment

A broader set of KPIs has been designed to measure the indirect and envisioned impact of EVOLVE2CARE across technical, financial and budgetary (fiscal), environmental, social and regulatory aspects, ensuring a comprehensive evaluation of the project's effects. It is not essential to achieve impact in every domain, but rather to establish a method for measuring impact across various areas. The Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) outlined in Table 3 below represent the expected outcomes of the experimentation, providing a clear framework for assessing the specific impact in each domain.

Table 3 - KPIs for Impact Assessment

Stake holder	Need	KPI
Technical	Usability - Innovations should be user-friendly, visually appealing, and engaging to end-users.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improving user acceptance/usability score and end-user engagement.
	Interoperability- Seamless integration of innovations into existing healthcare	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration Success Rate: Percentage of innovations

	<p>systems and pathways, ensuring technical compatibility.</p>	<p>successfully integrated into existing healthcare systems without major technical issues.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time to Full Integration: Average time required to achieve seamless interoperability between the innovation and existing healthcare pathways.
Technical	<p>Standardisation - Health tech innovations must adhere to established standards to ensure consistency, reliability, and compatibility across healthcare systems and devices.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standards Compliance Checklist Completion: Percentage of required standardisation criteria met by each individual innovation during development and deployment.
	<p>Privacy - Health tech innovations must ensure secure data ownership and protection, safeguarding users' personal and health information.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical implementation ensures user and data privacy and security.
	<p>Real-world Applicability - HealthTech innovations must address the practical needs and challenges of stakeholders, ensuring they are relevant and valuable in real-world settings.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Type and representativeness of stakeholders involved in assessing the knowledge gaps and needs addressed by the innovation.
Fiscal	<p>Faster development and launching of the innovations.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reducing by 3 months the time to market
	<p>Lower the high upfront costs of design and implementation of new innovations.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lowering development costs of products/services by 5%
	<p>Innovators and innovations need to prioritize equity and access, ensuring that products are available to all populations, while also having investment and commercialization pathways that are free from territorial inequalities, allowing for fair distribution across regions.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrate Partnership results on national/regional/ local strategies, programmes, and plans supporting synergies across policy areas towards health and care systems transformation.

	Stimulating investment in innovative care models and experimental approaches.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2M€ Unlocked in Healthcare Savings
Environmental	Innovations need to prioritize eco-friendliness by promoting responsible consumption and production practices, minimizing environmental impact throughout their lifecycle.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainability Compliance: innovations should adhere to eco-friendly standards, demonstrating responsible consumption and production practices throughout their development and lifecycle.
Social	Innovations should be designed to be culturally sensitive, inclusive, and accessible, addressing social and psychological factors to overcome stigma and cultural barriers for patients.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Percentage of innovations incorporating cultural sensitivity assessments, ensuring inclusivity in design, and accessibility.
Regulatory	Innovations need to align with both European and local legislations and regulations to ensure compliance and smooth integration into healthcare systems.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documentation and audits confirming adherence to European and national legal requirements.
	Regulatory Readiness Tracking: Ensuring early compliance alignment with EU and national regulations to prevent costly market entry delays.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of innovations that successfully meet regulatory milestones without compliance-related delays.
	Measuring progress toward regulatory approval, including clinical validation milestones, technical documentation compliance, and industry safety standards alignment.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Completion rate of key clinical validation milestones, ensuring adherence to technical and industry safety standards.